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Female creators, directors and screenwriters in TV fiction production in Spain (2000 to 2020): gender inequality and characteristics of the roles

This study analyses gender inequality in TV fiction production in Spain regarding the three key positions of responsibility, namely creators, directors, and screenwriters, and the characteristics of these roles. Firstly, we recorded the gender of all the individuals identified in the sample, which consists of all television series (N=546) broadcast from 2000 to 2020 on free-to-air television and streaming platforms. Secondly, the series in which women were involved were studied across years, channels, coverage, and genres. The results reveal that women are underrepresented in all three positions, averaging 31%. Although women creators have the highest rate of gender inequality, they have benefited the most from the arrival of streaming platforms in 2016. Furthermore, women predominantly work in mixed-gender teams with a male majority and rarely do they work solely or in all-female teams, especially among screenwriters.

Keywords: gender inequality; TV fiction; female authorship; female creators; Spanish TV fiction

1. Introduction

Throughout history, men have predominantly occupied leadership roles, leaving women to navigate various obstacles in their career progression, including the metaphorical "glass ceiling" that stifles the advancement of female talent across the audiovisual

sector. Consequently, this study investigates gender disparities within leadership positions: creators, directors, and screenwriters, within the Spanish television landscape. More precisely, it aims to scrutinise TV productions from 2000 to 2020, delving into the distinctive attributes linked with these roles. One of the justifications for research is the importance of culture in society. In this regard, TV series can be understood as symbolic cultural products that reflect values, beliefs, attitudes, and identities (Elena Galán-Fajardo 2007, Anna Tous-Rovirosa 2015). For this reason, it is crucial to understand the gender dynamics at play in creating TV shows and the lack of recognition of female authorship.

Although series are characterised by teamwork, we believe creators, directors, and screenwriters have greater responsibility regarding authorship. Our understanding of female authorship is shaped by scholars (Concepción Cascajosa-Virino 2015, Shelley Cobb 2015, Angela Martin 2003, Helen Warner 2023), who advocate for a new perspective on analysing female authorship amidst increasing female presence in the audiovisual industry. They argue that traditional male authorship theories do not adequately apply to female authorship due to women's underrepresentation and the lesser status of females in filmmaking. Moreover, Martin (2003) advocates for a shift in focus within feminist theory filmmaking to address female authorship, irrespective of whether their histories express a feminist perspective.

Consequently, our approach to analysing the creators, directors, and screenwriters of Spanish TV fiction is based on the professional characteristics of the roles listed in the credits of the series, which are the primary data sources for this research. We consider creators or showrunners responsible for the creative conception of the program. The role is the equivalent of a film director regarding authorship in cinema. However, since the term 'showrunner' is typically reserved for creators with a

proven track record of creative success and critical acclaim in TV shows (Cascajosa-Virino 2017), and considering the complexities involved in being a showrunner, this paper will use the term 'creator' instead. Directors are responsible for directing the entire series or chapters, including settings, editing, music, photography, and other formal and creative aspects of the process. However, unlike in film, the direction of television series entails less creative autonomy as it typically adheres to the vision set by the creators. Screenwriters are those who write the script for the series. According to Concepción Cascajosa-Virino and Natalia Martínez-Pérez (2016), Spanish screenwriters have found more opportunities to write for television than for cinema, which male authors dominate.

The study of gender inequality in the audiovisual sector has gained importance, reflecting growing academic and institutional interest in gender-based research. Recent data from AEC (2021) shows gender inequality in Spain's film industry: female screenwriters and directors comprised only 15% and 16% of the 222 feature films produced in 2020. Previous research in the early 21st century revealed similarly low female participation in key creative roles (Ana Martínez-Collado-Martínez and Ana Navarrete-Tudela 2011). Gender inequality persists across various roles in the film industry, with exceptions in traditionally female-led professions (costume design, hair and makeup). Music composition faces the highest disparity, which fell as low as 4% in 2017 (Sara Cuenca-Suárez 2022). This pattern extends globally, with women still underrepresented in leadership positions in the United States and Europe (Martha Lauzen 2019, Karen Ross 2014).

Despite increased female presence in recent decades, a significant gender gap remains in leadership roles. Gilles Fontaine (2022) analysed European TV fiction production, finding that female directors represented 22% and women comprised 36%

of active writers. Inequality increases when analysing the series in which women participate because more than one person is involved in directing or writing a project. In this vein, female directors were spread out in mixed-gender teams with a male majority. On average, women directed less fiction than men and were less likely to work as the sole director. Similarly, female screenwriters rarely wrote projects solely, and they were more likely than their male colleagues to write within mixed-gender teams dominated by men (Fontaine 2022). Additionally, academics have observed a collaborative culture among women, as they actively seek to involve other women in their work teams (Cascajosa-Virino 2017, Cobb 2015, María José Higuera-Ruiz 2019). This solidarity among women is significant in understanding female authorship in Spanish TV fiction.

This unequal phenomenon alludes to the concept of the "glass ceiling", a term widespread in gender studies since the 1980s (Lily Segerman-Peck 1991) and refers to the limitation women experience in being promoted to positions of responsibility in businesses and organisations. The glass ceiling is a metaphor that describes the possible and invisible barriers that prevent many personally and professionally capable women from attaining director positions and being promoted from within those positions (Marilyn Davidson and Cary Cooper 1992, Maite Sarrió et al. 2002). Although its origins lie in sociology and research into large businesses, the term can be extrapolated to any field in the cultural industries as a concept fully capable of explaining the invisible barriers contributing to the existing gender gap.

In the context of the audiovisual industry in Spain, previous studies have not only reported the gender gap in the film and television industry but also brought female authorship in films and television to the fore (Cascajosa-Virino 2015, Cascajosa-Virino and Martínez-Pérez 2016, Martínez-Collado-Martínez and Navarrete-Tudela 2011, Jose Luis Torres-Martín et al. 2021). Regarding the role of directors, there is relevant

research that analysed films directed by women throughout the history of European (Carmen Rodríguez and Eduardo Viñuela, 2011) and Spanish cinema to explore the characteristics of female authorship as a reference for future generations (Trinidad Núñez-Domínguez et al. 2012). It is worth mentioning the films directed by, among others, Margarita Aleixandre, Emma Cohen and Ana Mariscal from the 1950s to the 1980s, and later Pilar Miró (Trinidad Núñez-Domínguez 2010). Other studies also revealed that women have historically played a subordinate role in the audiovisual world, most notably in roles behind the camera (Torres-Martín et al. 2021).

For screenwriters, the profession enjoys much less stability in the audiovisual industry than that of the director, which remains the most relevant in creative terms. The unstable nature of writing positions means that women screenwriters face twofold discrimination compared with women directors, according to Cascajosa-Virino and Martínez-Pérez (2016). A report cited by these authors indicates that women represent less than 24% of all screenwriters. They mention notable female screenwriters like Ana Diosdado, Chus Gutiérrez, Ana Mariscal, María del Carmen Martínez-Román, Pilar Miró, Josefina Molina Reig, Carmen Rico Godoy, Margarita Robles, and Natividad Zaro Casanova, some of whom were also filmmakers. Alexis Kreager and Stephen Fellows (2023) found similar gender inequality among screenwriters in the UK.

Throughout Spain's history of audiovisual productions, men have predominantly held leadership roles in artistic direction (Fátima Arranz 2008, Angels Cruzado 2006). However, international studies have highlighted the creative contributions of women in audiovisual productions (Jorge Ruffinelli 2014, Rose Weitz 2016), offering narratives distinct from the male perspective. Women behind the camera are more likely to address feminist themes (Concepción Martínez-Tejedor 2008). Furthermore, female

leadership brings a new language to traditional cinematic discourse that has long been silenced by producers (Ignacio Prado 1998).

In terms of genre, the research underscores women's tendency to gravitate towards specific genres, particularly drama (Julia Hallam 2013), while their involvement in creating television comedies remains limited (Sarah Ralph and Brett Mills 2015). However, some female film directors have used comedy as a feminist strategy, challenging the notion that humour is gendered (Barbara Zecchi 2018).

1.1. Female authorship in Spain: industrial, social and cultural context

The historical, social and cultural context in Spain is crucial for understanding the gender inequality that women faced in accessing the audiovisual sector. Regarding the rise and evolution of feminism, the Franco dictatorship in the 1940s further suppressed feminist achievements that began during the Second Republic in the early 1930s. Despite the transition to democracy in the late 1970s, the feminist movement in Spain became entangled in theoretical debates, diminishing its societal recognition and nearly fading into insignificance by the early 21st century (Mercedes Carbayo-Abengózar, 2000).

In this historical context, women's difficulty accessing film studies during the dictatorship might explain their underrepresentation as filmmakers. On the contrary, female journalists and screenwriters had greater access to television studies and Spanish public television (RTVE), which became a talent pool for female authorship (Cascajosa-Virino, 2015). RTVE operated as a monopolistic broadcaster and fiction producer until the emergence of private television channels in the 1990s, a pivotal decade for fiction because these channels not only increased TV shows but also incentivised the production of the public broadcaster in the subsequent decades. Nevertheless, female

filmmakers consider television an alternative to compensate for the limited opportunities in cinema, which has traditionally been viewed as more prestigious than television (Cascajosa-Virino 2019, Perkins and Schreiber 2019).

This research focuses on the first two decades of the 21st century, a period characterised by the gradual development and consolidation of television fiction in Spain within an industrial context marked by the digitisation of television consumption in 2007 and the economic crisis that impacted TV fiction until 2015 (Cascajosa-Virino, 2018). In this context, the law to promote gender equality in 2007 in Spain led to an increase in the presence of female creators in Spain, professionals who found in television a sector within the audiovisual industry to build a more stable career than in cinema, especially with the arrival of streaming platforms in Spain in 2016 (Cascajosa-Virino, 2017). Foreign platforms such as Netflix, HBO, and Prime Video arrived later in Spain, but their model stimulated local companies like Movistar+ and Atresmedia, which developed their own streaming platforms by subscription. For instance, Atresplayer Premium premiered shows that later aired on the free-to-air channel Antena 3, which both belong to the same media corporation.

During the second decade of the 21st century, Claire Perkins and Michele Schreiber (2019) observe a 'golden age of television for women', suggesting that the critical and commercial success of TV shows created, directed, and written by women and addressed to female audiences might contribute positively to feminism. However, scholars like Perkins and Schreiber (2019) and Cobb (2024) raise critical questions about whether this 'golden age' of women on television is indeed part of the loop of popular feminism, as theorised by Sarah Banet-Weiser (2018). This form of feminism has garnered significant visibility precisely because it avoids confrontation and neglects to challenge the neoliberal context that perpetuates inequalities. According to the latter

author, popular feminism emerges within an economy of visibility, which stems from the ethos of post-feminism—a movement characterised by an adverse reaction towards feminism portrayed in cinema and television (Angela McRobbie 2009). Therefore, by redirecting feminist author theory to analyse this golden age of television for women, it becomes possible to critically examine women's authorship in both film (Cobb 2015, Martin 2003, Warner 2022, Duncan Wheeler 2016) and television (Cobb 2024, Cascajosa-Virino 2017, 2019, Francisco J. López-Rodríguez and Irene Raya-Bravo 2019). In this sense, Cobb (2015) considers female authorship as a metaphor for the struggle for female agency in a post-feminist environment that might impede such agency.

In Spain, Teresa Fernández-Valdés is a showrunner that could be considered an example of the golden age of television for women in Spain. On the one hand, Fernández-Valdés is a creator at the television production company Bambú, aligning with the practices of international showrunners in the television platform context. On the other hand, she advocates for including a more significant number of women in collaborative creative teams. However, her TV shows connect with a post-feminist ethos that confirms the economy of the visibility that fuels a form of popular feminism devoid of political commitment. While Fernández-Valdés acknowledges these criticisms, she emphasises that her primary goal is to entertain rather than educate the audience (López-Rodríguez and Raya-Bravo, 2019). In the realm of cinema during the early 21st century, several Spanish directors, including Icíar Bollaín, Isabel Coixet, Ángeles González-Sinde, Belén Macías, Silvia Munt, and Gracia Querejeta, achieved notable success without overtly addressing feminist themes (Wheeler 2016). However, directors such as Belén Macías (with *My Prison Yard*, 2008) and Silvia Munt (with *Pretextos*, 2008) effectively portrayed the challenges faced by real women, even within

a post-feminist context, by employing melodrama—a genre often criticised by reviewers (Wheeler 2016).

Finally, and regarding social context, Spain witnessed a pivotal moment for feminism in 2017, particularly fourth-wave feminism, for two primary reasons. Firstly, the social cohesion sparked by support for a rape victim during the San Fermín celebrations in Pamplona solidified the concept of sisterhood, an essential aspect of fourth-wave feminism (Rosa Cobo 2019). This solidarity led to widespread protests against sexual violence, a global problem that exerts a powerful mechanism of control over women. Secondly, the #MeToo movement gained momentum globally, ignited by the scandal involving film producer Harvey Weinstein's alleged sexual assaults on actresses. The movement utilised social media platforms to amplify women's voices and causes on an unprecedented scale, reminiscent of past feminist movements such as the suffragette movement and 1970s radical feminism (Cobo 2019). The 2018 International Women's Day also saw historic demonstrations in Spain, including a feminist general strike.

2. Objectives and methodology

The main objective of this research is to measure gender inequality in key creative roles in TV fiction production in Spain and to study the main characteristics of these positions by years, channels, coverage and genre. To that end, this work addresses three specific objectives, analysing 1) creators, 2) directors, and 3) screenwriters. These three creative roles were classified as follows: 1) creators develop the narrative idea (series created by); 2) directors are responsible for directing the entire process; 3) screenwriters write the script. Although the specific objectives could be integrated into one, a structure of three objectives is proposed to facilitate the analysis of the three roles.

Regarding selection criteria, all series aired on free-to-air TV and SVOD (Subscription Video on Demand) platforms have been included, covering the first two decades of the 21st century. Thus, the whole sample is made up of n=546 Spanish TV shows that were released between 2000 and 2020 and broadcast both on the 25 (n=25) free-to-air television (national and regional) and on the 11 (n=11) streaming platforms that premiered series since 2016 (see table 1). The inclusion criterion was the platform where the series' first premiered. However, series like *Velvet* initially debuted on Antena 3, and were later distributed on platforms such as Atresplayer, Movistar, Netflix, HBO España, Amazon Prime Video, and Filmin. This highlights the dual role of networks and platforms as both producers and distributors.

A genuine ad hoc methodology was used to code the sample in two steps. Firstly, to measure gender inequality, the individuals (creators, directors, and screenwriters) of each programme (n=546) were identified and categorised by gender to measure the frequency of gender inequality in the positions of creators, directors and screenwriters. Authors experienced coding and conducting content analysis on Spanish television series carried out the coding sample. To that end, the first coder searched archives of digital newspapers that publish television listings and encyclopaedic resources. Information from digital catalogues available on the SVOD platforms and television channels was also used to code the sample. Emphasis was placed on gathering data on the entire professional teams involved, given that the creative, directing and writing teams can often consist of more than one person. Once the coder transcribed the data to the Excel spreadsheet, the second coder checked the reliability and accuracy of the sample until both coders reached complete agreement on the data. The classification by sex was solely based on biological factors, acknowledging the limitations it implies regarding sexual diversity.

Table 1. Sample of the research

NATIONAL TV (AIR/OPEN)	REGIONAL TV (AIR/OPEN)	SVOD (SUBSCRIPTION)
Antena 3	Canal 9, A Punt (Valencian C.)	Atreseries
Canal+	Canal Sur, Canal 2 (Andalusia)	Atresplayer Premium
Clan	TV3, Canal 33 (Catalonia)	Filmin
Cuatro	Aragón TV (Aragon)	Flooxer
La Sexta	CMMTV (Castile-La Mancha)	HBO
Neox	ETB1, ETB2 (Basque Country)	Movistar+
Telecinco	IB3 (Balearic Islands)	Netflix
TNT	Telemadrid (Madrid)	Orange TV
TVE (La 1)	Televisión Canaria (Canary Islands)	Playz
TVE (La 2)	TPA (Asturias)	Prime Video
	TVG (Galicia)	#0
Total 10	Total 15	Total 11

Secondly, and once the gender inequality of the 546 productions had been measured in terms of the total number of people, only the series with the involvement of at least one woman were analysed to identify the following: a) year of broadcast; b) name of broadcast channel or platform; c) broadcast coverage (national or regional); d) genre. Therefore, the analysis of these variables was conducted on a sample of n=88 (out of 546) series for female creators, n=149 (out of 546) for female directors, and n=355 (out of 546) for female scriptwriters. Data was collected using Excel software, and the authors performed subsequent statistical operations. Finally, this paper will provide a concise qualitative analysis of paradigmatic examples of creators and TV shows to contextualise female authorship in Spanish television.

3. Results

Gender inequality persists across the positions of creator, director, and screenwriter. Women are underrepresented (31%), while men dominate all three positions with an average of 69% (see chart 1), indicating that there are proportionally more than twice as many men as women in these roles of responsibility.

Chart 1: Gender inequality by total amount of people

Source: author's own

When examining the professions individually across 546 series (see Chart 1), the most concerning disparity arises in the role of female creators, with 18.8% (105 women) of the total. While the frequency of female directors is 34.4% (210 women), it is slightly higher, and men still dominate this role by more than two to one. In terms of screenwriters, among the 3088 individuals involved in scriptwriting teams, only 29.3% (905) are women, once again showcasing a two-to-one disparity favouring men.

3.1 Women as Creators

Once the gender inequality among creators (18.8%) has been analysed regarding the total number of individuals, we focus on series with at least one woman in their creative teams. The inequality is more significant (16.1%) than the total number of individuals because the 105 female creators are spread across 88 of the 546 TV shows (see chart 2).

Female creators often collaborate in mixed-gender pairs or teams when creating a series. In this way, 22% (n=19) of the series were created solely by women, either collectively (3 cases) or individually (16 cases). This suggests that women tend to develop separately and rarely in exclusively female teams (see chart 2). Additionally, it is observed that 78% (n=69) of creators mainly work in duos or mixed-gender teams with a male majority.

A notable example of a mixed-gender creators' team is the production company Bambú, established by Ramón Campos and Teresa Fernández-Valdés in 2007, coinciding with the rise of digital television in Spain. Alongside Gema R. Neira, they have emerged as three of the most prominent showrunners in Spanish television. They are involved in 15 of 88 series featuring a woman in a creative role, both for free-to-air television and SVOD. While they primarily produce dramas or historical series for a broad audience, they have also crafted series for women audiences, such as *Velvet* and *Cable Girls*. However, both shows lack a feminist political stance. For instance, *Cable Girls*, set in 1920s Madrid, follows the lives of four working women at a telephone company navigating romantic challenges and pursuing independence in a conservative society. Despite portraying empowered female characters, the series could be interpreted as post-feminist due to its omission of addressing the patriarchal power structures that perpetuate women's inequality in employment access and gender violence (López Rodríguez and Raya Bravo, 2019).

Virginia Yagüe stands out as an individual creator thanks to her three series on free-to-air television, two of which are aimed at female audiences, and her activism against gender inequality in the Spanish audiovisual industry (Cascajosa-Virino, 2017). With a long trajectory as a screenwriter since the 90s, she has become a key figure in Spain, advocating for the inclusion of more women in creative teams. *La Señora* [*The*

Lady] premiered in 2008 on the free-to-air public channel La 1 and stands as Yagüe's most successful show. It is a romantic and historical melodrama set in the 1920s, depicting the journey of a wealthy and empowered woman who unexpectedly undertakes the family business amid a backdrop of class struggle. *The Lady* illustrates the complexities of agency in female authorship and Yagüe's efforts to help women tell their own stories. The series depicts the challenges that white privileged women face through the lens of femininity and lacks a political feminist perspective, leaning more towards post-feminism despite the historical context that may justify the subjectivity of traditional femininity.

SVOD platforms have allowed film directors like Isabel Coixet and Manuela Burló Moreno and actresses like Ana Milan and Leticia Dolera, who have prominent careers in Spain, to release their television series. In most of these productions, the creators collaborate with mixed-gender teams and do not specifically explore female themes. However, two series could be considered part of the golden age of women in television, such as Leticia Dolera's *Vida Perfecta* [*Perfect Life*] (Movistar+) and María López Castaño's *Valeria* (Netflix). Both have been created solely by women and feature predominantly female teams in direction and screenplay and share similarities with *Girls* by Lena Dunham or *Fleabag* by Phoebe Waller-Bridge. On one hand, *Perfect Life* explores the complexity of white and privileged women's lives, including their identity crises, romantic relationships, job insecurity, sexual relationships, homosexuality, and motherhood. According to Dolera (Ana Pastor 2019), she aimed not to create a feminist series but a smart, funny, and insightful narrative about women's challenges in the midlife crisis. On the other hand, María López Castaño adapts Elisabet Benavent's novel *Valeria*, which reinforces public femininity that provides intimacy, friendship and revelation for privileged women. Both series lack a critical and intersectional feminist

perspective on labour or romantic love. Although *Perfect Life* might present more gender awareness than *Valeria*, both series reflect characteristics of popular feminism that emerged from post-feminism.

Finally, *Les de l'Hoquei* [The Hockey Girls] stands out as a series with a feminist commitment aimed at teenage girls and developed by a female team in creation, direction, and screenplay. The series addresses gender injustice in women's sports and explores topics such as abortion, homosexuality, and challenging gender stereotypes. Although it initially criticises patriarchy for women's issues, the political commitment fades as the plot progresses, focusing more on romantic and friendship relationships. The series premiered on the regional channel of Catalonia and is now available on Netflix.

Chart 2: Women as Creators

Source: author's own

A longitudinal analysis indicates ups and downs in the number of series created by women over time, reaching a peak in 2019 before declining in 2020, the year of the pandemic. In the analysed period, women produced an average of 4.3 series. However, this average increased by two points during the emergence of streaming platforms (2016-2020). In this context, streaming platforms have led to a slight increase in opportunities for women creators of shows, reducing inequality from 14% (from 2000 to 2015) to 27.7% over the last five years. Concerning SVOD, the Spanish telecommunications company Movistar+ debuted the highest number of series created by women (7), while Prime Video premiered the fewest (2).

In contrast, in the realm of free-to-air television, gender inequality has experienced a smaller decrease compared to SVODs (from 14% to 17.6%) over the last five years. Notably, the private free-to-air channel Antena 3 produced the highest number of series (7) created by women during the last five years and from 2000 to 2020, accounting for 26% (26 cases) of all its shows. The private broadcast channel Telecinco had only 13.4% (11 cases), and La 1 had a similar proportion, with 13.4% (11 cases). In this regard, it is surprising that La 1, a publicly owned television channel, has the lowest number of series created by women. Finally, 19.3% of the series featuring women as creators were broadcast by public regional channels.

Regarding genre (chart 2), drama dominates in 72.7%. Comedy and fringe genres, such as dramedy, appear in 27.3% of the productions created or co-created by women. This trend could be attributed to the tendency for drama series to have higher international marketability than comedies. However, there are noteworthy sitcoms, including *Escoba!* (2011) and *Caseiros* (2014), both premiered on the Galician regional television TVG and the biopic *By Ana Milán*, created by actress Ana Milán herself for Atresplayer in 2020.

3.2. Women as Directors

The 210 women (34.4%) have directed 149 TV shows, accounting for 27.3% of the series. Like the creator position, gender inequality increases by 7% (34.4% to 27.3%) due to multiple individuals directing across mixed-gender teams. Additionally, 58% of female directors primarily worked in mixed-gender teams where males were predominant, and only 25% of women were directors in gender-balanced teams (chart 3).

Furthermore, 17% of TV shows were solely directed by women (chart 3), either

individually (n=22) or as part of a female team (n=3). Women were proportionally less likely to work as the sole director than female creators. In this line, two patterns emerge: either a single woman directs all the episodes of the series (i.e. Isabel Coixet in *Foodie Love* and Mar Coll in *To Kill the Father*), or a woman directs some or several episodes of the series together with other women (i.e. *Madres, Amor y Vida* [Mothers, Love and Life] or *Perfect Life*).

Women who direct all episodes generally have only one work, mostly consisting of miniseries or series that do not extend beyond the first season on free-to-air television. The directors combine directing episodes in several TV series with filmmaking, like Mar Coll, Gracia Querejeta, Silvia Queer, Eva Lesmes, Belen Macías, Ana Murugarren, Silvia Munt, and Mar Olid, among others. Additionally, Sandra Gallego, Begoña Álvarez Rojas, and Abigail Schaaff stand out as three television series directors who have exclusively worked in television during the two decades analysed, contributing to recognised successful and critically acclaimed TV shows in Spain.

In the realm of SVOD, two examples might fit into a strategy to elevate the cultural prestige of television in Spain through the involvement of auteur filmmakers such as Isabel Coixet and Mar Coll. In both cases, directors also serve as the creators regarding authorship. On the one hand, Isabel Coixet, one of Spain's most internationally successful filmmakers, introduced *Foodie Love* (HBO, 2020), a miniseries delving into the creative universe of gastronomy on an international scale. Coixet defined her miniseries as an 'auteur series' because she had the same creative autonomy as when working as a filmmaker (Valerio Caruso 2019). She believes that directors often lose their creative autonomy when working in television because the creators set the project guidelines. On the other hand, Mar Coll created the family drama *To Kill the Father* for Movistar+, another 'auteur series' that was a failure in

terms of audience but allowed her to express her creativity in the television medium, which in Spain offers more opportunities than cinema (Cascajosa-Virino 2019).

Regarding all-women teams, stand out in the series addressed to female audience *Madres. Amor y Vida* [*Mothers. Love and Life*]. It was created and written by two males (Aitor Gabilondo and Joan Barbero) and directed separately in each chapter by Juana Macías, Mar Olid, Abigail Schaaff, Roser Aguilar and Gracia Querejeta. The series explores the lives of white women facing motherhood in a hospital through a melodramatic portrayal of femineity that includes friendship and romance.

Paradoxically, in *Mothers. Love and Life*, two men, write about motherhood from their experiences as sons. Aware of the limited opportunities for women in television, both creators chose to entrust the TV show's direction to a female team (Laura García 2019). By reinforcing the stereotype of self-sacrificing mother and femininity, the series focuses on the perceived need for women to find revelation and relief in contemporary times. Thus, the series adopts a post-feminist perspective by assigning the neoliberal discourse of care work primarily to so-called aspirational and devoted mothers.

A longitudinal analysis indicates significant variability in the participation of female directors in TV series (see chart 3), averaging 7.4 series directed by women annually—almost double the number of female creators. Between 2000 and 2004, approximately four series were directed by women on average. Series directed by women show fluctuations throughout the period, with peaks exceeding ten series in 2009 and 2011 and from 2018 onwards.

Chart 3: Women as Directors

Source: author's own

Regarding channels and platforms, 86.6% were created for conventional television channels, while 13.4% were for SVOD platforms, a percentage lower than creators from 2000 to 2020. In contrast to female creators, SVODs have not meant more opportunities for Spanish female directors compared to free-to-air television from 2016 to 2020. In this sense, the Spanish telecommunication company Movistar+ and Netflix premiered the most women-directed series. Furthermore, Telecinco, the private broadcast television network, aired the highest number of series (6) directed by women during the last five years. However, in the two decades analysed, Antena 3 aired the highest amount of series on private free-to-air channels (23%), followed by Telecinco

(14%) and La 1 (14%). Notably, 30.9% of the series involving women were broadcast by regional channels, highlighting the significance of regional television for women directors. However, regionally released shows typically have a smaller audience than series aired nationwide.

In terms of genre, the series and miniseries directed by women are primarily dramas (61.1% of cases). Only 19.5% of the series directed or co-directed by women are comedies, sitcoms or fringe formats, such as dramedies.

3.3. Women as screenwriters

The screenwriting role shows the least gender inequality compared to female creators and directors. This is because 905 women (29.3% of the total) are involved in multiple projects, having written scripts for 65% (n=355) of the 546 series sampled (chart 4).

The average number of series featuring women in the writing teams is 17.7, significantly higher than that for creators (4.3) and directors (7.4). While this may appear positive, it could also be seen as unfavourable. Despite women's higher participation as screenwriters compared to creators and directors, they tend to work in mixed-gender teams with a male majority, indicating a dispersion of female talent. Further analysis revealed that writing teams are generally larger than creator and director teams, with some comprising as many as 14 writers. However, only 4.75% of the series were exclusively written by women, individually or as part of all-female teams.

Given that scriptwriting is mainly carried out in mixed-gender teams, it is worth highlighting the names of some screenwriters involved in series such as Gema R. Neira (19 series), Lidia Fraga (12 series), and María José García, Ángela Obón, Araceli Gonda and Esther Martínez-Lobato, who worked on approximately seven series each. It

is worth noting that a mixed-gender duo, Leticia Dolera and Manuel Burque, wrote together *Perfect Life* (Movistar+ in 2019). Finally, the exclusively female writing teams of *Las del Hòquei* and *Valeria* stand out, as they are the only two series created, directed, and written exclusively by women and for women.

Chart 4: Women as screenwriters

Source: author's own

A longitudinal study reveals a progressive increase but with fluctuations during the crisis period (2009-2016). However, while only six series featured female screenwriters in 2002, the count surged to 30 in 2020, marking a more than twofold increase over the years (chart 4). Female scriptwriters remained steady during the

pandemic year. In terms of channels, series in which women participated were predominantly aired on free-to-air television (89.4% of the total), compared to 10.6% of series shown on SVOD platforms over the two decades. When comparing free-to-air television and SVOD over the last five years, no increase is noted in the percentage of series written by female screenwriters. Regarding genre, drama remains the predominant genre, accounting for 65.4% of the total. Comedy accounts for 34.6% of the series in this category (chart 4).

4. Discussions

Gender inequality persists in Spanish TV fiction throughout the first two decades of the 21st century. Men dominate in creation, direction, and screenwriting (69% vs 31%), with women creators being the most unequal among the three roles. However, female creators have benefited the most from the emergence of streaming platforms since 2016 (Cascajosa-Virino 2017, López-Rodríguez and Raya-Bravo 2019). The same cannot be said for female directors and screenwriters, where it is observed that the levels of inequality remain similar with the arrival of SVOD platforms.

Furthermore, in line with Fontaine (2023), women were predominantly integrated into mixed-gender teams, typically with a male majority, and only a scant minority of the series was created and directed solely by women, such as Virginia Yagüe, Leticia Dolera, or Isabel Coixet. Regarding the profession of screenwriting, the results are paradoxical because it exhibits the least inequality but concentrates a greater dispersion for women, to the extent that it is rare to find series exclusively written by a team of women like *Valeria* or *Les del Hòcquet*.

The results on gender inequality align with previous studies, where it has also been observed that television shows lower inequality than the film industry (Cascajosa-Virino and Martínez-Pérez, 2016, Cuenca-Suarez 2022, Fontaine 2022, Kreager and

Fellows 2023, Lauzen 2019, Simone 2019). Similar to cinema trends, there was a decrease in the number of female creators and directors during the pandemic year (AEC 2021), while the number of female screenwriters saw a slight improvement. Regarding genres, women are relegated, just as in the case of the UK, to drama (Ralph and Mills 2015), and any comedies made are an exception (i.e. *By Ana Milán*).

These findings of this research quantitatively complement the academic research of Spanish scholars that have contributed to our understanding of the context and challenges that women have faced in terms of education, funding, and independence in authorship and management in Spain (Cascajosa-Virino 2015, 2017, 2019, López-Rodríguez and Raya-Bravo 2019).

5. Conclusions

The analysis of gender inequality in Spanish TV fiction throughout the two decades of the 21st century reveals a persistent glass ceiling for female creators, directors, and screenwriters, hindering the progress of female authorship. Despite women creators facing significant gender disparity, there has been a modest improvement (13%) since streaming platforms emerged in 2016 compared to the first fifteen years of the study. However, female directors and screenwriters have not seen substantial improvement, highlighting the ongoing need for initiatives to address this imbalance.

The encouraging aspect of these findings lies in the modest reduction of inequality observed within the creator role, which holds the most significant responsibility for authorship compared to directing and writing in television. Despite female creators often working in predominantly male-dominated creative environments, their increasing presence in this capacity aligns with a growing recognition of television's value as a medium for fiction in Spain, and it aligns with the transformation

of the Spanish television ecosystem with the arrival of the SVOD. This recognition extends to both audience appreciation and critical acclaim, indicating a broader acknowledgement of the contributions made by women to the Spanish television industry. Given that this research has demonstrated that the television industry in Spain exhibits less inequality than the film industry, it is pertinent to shift the focus towards television rather than film to gain a deeper understanding of the characteristics and significance of female authorship.

In this regard, three characteristics linked to women's participation in television can be identified: series without a female voice, series with a female voice created by women to women, and auteur series. Firstly, the presence of women in creative teams, whether mixed or male-dominated, does not guarantee the existence of a female or feminist voice in the resulting series. Most series, primarily in the drama genre, address themes that may fall outside the scope of feminist film theory analysis. For Martin (2003), analysing these women's production, creative, and aesthetic work is crucial, even if their stories lack a female voice. The cases of Teresa Fernández Valdés and Gema R. Neira, belonging to the Bambú production company alongside Ramón Campos, exemplify the increasing relevance of female showrunners in Spain. This underscores the importance of understanding the context and challenges these women face in production, funding, and issues related to the conceptualisation and aesthetic characteristics of the series they create. This way, a more comprehensive overview of female authorship can be provided.

Secondly, there has been a rise in series crafted for and aimed at women. This trend aligns with what Perkins and Schreiber (2019) dubbed the 'golden age of television for women' amid the transformation and digitalisation of the television landscape. Creators such as Leticia Dolera, María López-Castaño, Teresa Fernández-

Valdés, Gema R. Neira, and Virginia Yagüe are examples that highlight the difficulties in representing female agency in a post-feminist or popular feminism context, showing the challenge of representing feminist series with political commitment (Cobb 2015, Banet-Weiser 2018). They are also examples of the collaborative work that characterises women creators. Although Teresa Fernández-Valdés and Virginia Yagüe are making efforts to increase the presence of women in their creative teams, and their commitment to addressing women's issues is growing, their series lacks a political feminist focus. According to Banet-Weiser (2018), this is one of the pitfalls of popular feminism: assuming that a more significant number of women will automatically result in feminist series. However, the increasing number of women in these roles allows for a deeper qualitative analysis of these series to explore the economic, cultural, and agency complexities that influence female authorship in Spain. The lack of political commitment observed in the series contrasts with a more active and contesting feminism in Spain, especially between 2016 and 2020, which is not reflected in these series. This discrepancy highlights the complexity of the manifestations of popular feminism and its relationship with media representations in Spain. Given that women are more likely to create television series with a feminist perspective, achieving gender equity in the Spanish television industry is crucial.

Finally, platforms like Movistar+ and HBO have tried to legitimise television over cinema, producing auteur series directed by renowned female filmmakers such as Isabel Coixet and Mar Coll. This strategy is not intended to improve opportunities for women filmmakers. Instead, it represents an effort to enhance television's prestige by adhering to the convention of auteur cinema, which men have historically dominated. Consequently, television's value in Spain is steeped in a masculine ethos. The career paths of these directors reveal notable differences: while Coixet, taking advantage of her

established reputation, chooses television as the best medium to tell the story of *Foodie Love*, Mar Coll embarks on *To Kill the Father* because television offers more opportunities than film. Generally speaking, women filmmakers who direct series turn to television because they often face more significant obstacles in pursuing their creative projects within film. This also fuels the debate about independence, creative freedom and the value of female authorship in television compared to film.

International and local SVOD platforms have significantly transformed the television landscape, changing entertainment consumption by offering viewers a more comprehensive selection of on-demand series. These new players have provided a greater variety of TV shows reflecting Spanish society's diverse identities and subjectivities. Nevertheless, when contrasting authorship crafted by males and females, the inequality remains strikingly pronounced in both free-to-air and SVODs. The diachronic analysis reveals fluctuations, suggesting that neither the digital transformation of the television ecosystem in 2007 nor the commitment of public television to fiction during the first decade of the 21st century, nor even the law to promote gender equality in 2007, have managed to ensure equity in authorship. Furthermore, the economic crisis that affected fiction production in Spain until 2015 could explain the ups and downs observed during the central years of the analysed period (2009-2015).

In streaming and free-to-air television, the SVOD platform Movistar+ and the private network Antena 3, both Spanish-owned, lead the premieres of TV shows with female authorship. Overall, the private free-to-air television channel Antena 3 has led the production of series involving women's participation over the past two decades, including those led by standout showrunners Teresa Fernández-Valdés and Gema R. Neira from the production company Bambú. Additionally, Antena 3 belongs to the

media conglomerate Atresmedia, which launched its own subscription platforms, Atreseries and Atresplayer Premium, to capitalise on distributing television series and other content. In contrast, the public television La 1 stands out for its lack of commitment to female authorship. These results are disheartening considering the significant role of fictional TV series as symbolic cultural products, as these shows should be understood as a reflection of society, particularly within the public broadcaster.

A logical progression in this research would involve thoroughly examining gender inequality trends in the present decade to assess the influence of SVOD platforms on traditional television. Additionally, future studies could delve into qualitative analyses of female authorship, drawing from the characteristics identified in this research. This would entail exploring Spanish series created by women, regardless of their feminist voice, and those specifically aimed at female audiences. Lastly, there is a need to investigate further the concept of author series within female authorship from a feminist perspective.

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